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Direct Infusion Workflow

Overall study design

Title of the study	TDP-43 alters sphingolipid metabolism and the fatty acid composition of ether-linked phospholipids in neurons		
Document creation date	02/16/2026	Principal investigator	Dirk Fitzner
Institution	University Medical Hospital Göttingen, Department of Neurology, Germany	Corresponding Email	dirk.fitzner@med.uni-goettingen.de
Is the workflow targeted or untargeted?	Untargeted	Clinical	No

Lipid extraction

Extraction method	2-phase system	pH adjustment	None
2-phase system	2-step extraction	Were internal standards added prior extraction?	Yes

Analytical platform

Ionization additives	Acetic acid, Methylamine	Detector	Mass spectrometer
MS type	Orbitrap	MS vendor	Thermo
Direct type	Chip	MS Level	MS ¹ , MS ²
Mass resolution for detected ion at MS ¹	High resolution	Resolution at m/z 200 at MS ¹	280000
Mass accuracy in ppm at MS ¹	1	Recording mode of raw data at MS ¹	Centroid mode
Mass window for precursor ion isolation (in Da total isolation window)	1	Mass resolution for detected ion at MS ²	High resolution
Resolution at m/z 200 at MS ²	17500	Mass accuracy in ppm at MS ²	3
Recording mode of raw data at MS ²	Centroid mode	Was/Were additional dimension/techniques used	No

Quality control

Blanks	Yes	Type of Blanks	Extraction blank
Quality control	Yes	Type of QC sample	Reference material

Method qualification and validation

Method validation	Yes	Lipid recovery	Yes
Dynamic quantification range	Yes	Limit of quantitation (LOQ)/Limit of detection (LOD)	Yes
Precision	Yes	Accuracy	No
Guidelines followed	None		

Reporting

Are reported raw data uploaded into repository?	Available on request	Are metadata available?	No
Raw data upload	No		

Sample Descriptions

Cortical neurons from rat / Rat / Cells

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C
Instant sample preparation	No	Storage temperature	-80 °C
Additives	None	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Additional preservation methods	No	Biobank samples	No

Lipid Class Descriptions

1) PG[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PG	MS Level for identification	MS ¹ , MS ²
Identification level	Molecular species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M-H]-
Isotope correction at MS ¹	Type 2	MS ² adduct	[M-H]-

Fragments for identification

Fragment name

FA1(+O)

FA2(+O)

Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ¹ verified by standard	No
MS ² verified by standard	No	Background check at MS ¹	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes
Which assumptions were presumed?	Chemical formula constraints	Check on:	Isobaric overlap
Limit of detection	S/N ratio	Lipid Identification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes		

1) PG[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			

Internal standard

PG 34:0;0 (17:0;0/17:0;0)

Endogenous subclass

PG

Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	LipotypeXplorer
Batch correction	No		

2) CE[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	CE	MS Level for identification	MS ¹ , MS ²
Identification level	Molecular species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M+NH4] ⁺
Isotope correction at MS ¹	Type 2	MS ² adduct	[M+H] ⁺
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
-FA1-H2O			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ¹ verified by standard	No
MS ² verified by standard	No	Background check at MS ¹	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes
Which assumptions were presumed?	Chemical formula constraints	Check on:	Isobaric overlap
Limit of detection	S/N ratio	Lipid Identification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Nomenclature for fragment ions	No		

2) CE[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
CE 20:0;0		CE	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Batch correction	No		

3) Cer[M+CH3COO]⁻ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	Cer	MS Level for identification	MS ¹
Identification level	Species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M+CH3COO] ⁻
Isotope correction at MS ¹	Type 2	MS ¹ verified by standard	No
Background check at MS ¹	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes
Which assumptions were presumed?	Chemical formula constraints	Limit of detection	S/N ratio
Lipid Identification Software	Lipotype Xplorer	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes		

3) Cer[M+CH3COO]⁻ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
Cer 35:1;O2 (18:1;O2/17:0;0)		Cer	

Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Batch correction	No		

4) HexCer[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	HexCer	MS Level for identification	MS ¹
Identification level	Species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M+CH3COO]-
Isotope correction at MS ¹	Type 2	MS ¹ verified by standard	No
Background check at MS ¹	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes
Which assumptions were presumed?	Chemical formula constraints	Limit of detection	S/N ratio
Lipid Identification Software	Lipotype Xplorer	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes		

4) HexCer[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
HexCer 30:1;O2 (18:1;O2/12:0;0)	HexCer		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Batch correction	No		

5) DG[M+NH4]+ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	DG	MS Level for identification	MS ¹ , MS ²
Identification level	Molecular species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M+NH4]+
Isotope correction at MS ¹	Type 2	MS ² adduct	[M+H]+
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
-FA1(-H)-(H2O+NH3)			
-FA2(-H)-(H2O+NH3)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ¹ verified by standard	No
MS ² verified by standard	No	Background check at MS ¹	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes
Which assumptions were presumed?	Chemical formula constraints	Check on:	Isobaric overlap
Limit of detection	S/N ratio	Lipid Identification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes

Nomenclature for fragment ions Yes

5) DG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
DG 34:0;0 (17:0;0/17:0;0)		DG	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Batch correction	No		

6) LPC[M+CH3COO]⁻ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPC	MS Level for identification	MS ¹
Identification level	Species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M+CH3COO] ⁻
Isotope correction at MS ¹	Type 2	MS ¹ verified by standard	No
Background check at MS ¹	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes
Which assumptions were presumed?	Chemical formula constraints	Limit of detection	S/N ratio
Lipid Identification Software	Lipotype Xplorer	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes		

6) LPC[M+CH3COO]⁻ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
LPC 12:0;0		LPC	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Batch correction	No		

7) LPC O[M+CH3COO]⁻ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPC O	MS Level for identification	MS ¹
Identification level	Species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M+CH3COO] ⁻
Isotope correction at MS ¹	Type 2	MS ¹ verified by standard	No
Background check at MS ¹	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes
Which assumptions were presumed?	Chemical formula constraints	Limit of detection	S/N ratio

Lipid Identification Software	Lipotype Xplorer	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes		

7) LPC O[M+CH₃COO]⁻ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
LPC 12:0;0		LPC O	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Batch correction	No		

8) LPC P[M+CH₃COO]⁻ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPC P	MS Level for identification	MS ¹
Identification level	Species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M+CH ₃ COO] ⁻
Isotope correction at MS ¹	Type 2	MS ¹ verified by standard	No
Background check at MS ¹	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes
Which assumptions were presumed?	Chemical formula constraints	Limit of detection	S/N ratio
Lipid Identification Software	Lipotype Xplorer	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes		

8) LPC P[M+CH₃COO]⁻ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
LPC 12:0;0		LPC P	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Batch correction	No		

9) LPE[M-H]⁻ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPE	MS Level for identification	MS ¹
Identification level	Species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M-H] ⁻
Isotope correction at MS ¹	Type 2	MS ¹ verified by standard	No

Background check at MS ¹	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes
Which assumptions were presumed?	Chemical formula constraints	Limit of detection	S/N ratio
Lipid Identification Software	Lipotype Xplorer	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes		

9) LPE[M-H]⁻ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
LPE 17:1;0		LPE	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Batch correction	No		

10) LPE O[M-H]⁻ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPE O	MS Level for identification	MS ¹
Identification level	Species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M-H] ⁻
Isotope correction at MS ¹	Type 2	MS ¹ verified by standard	No
Background check at MS ¹	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes
Which assumptions were presumed?	Chemical formula constraints	Limit of detection	S/N ratio
Lipid Identification Software	Lipotype Xplorer	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes		

10) LPE O[M-H]⁻ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
LPE 17:1;0		LPE O	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Batch correction	No		

11) LPE P[M-H]⁻ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPE P	MS Level for identification	MS ¹
Identification level	Species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M-H]-
Isotope correction at MS ¹	Type 2	MS ¹ verified by standard	No
Background check at MS ¹	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes
Which assumptions were presumed?	Chemical formula constraints	Limit of detection	S/N ratio
Lipid Identification Software	Lipotype Xplorer	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes		

11) LPE P[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
LPE 17:1;0		LPE P	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Batch correction	No		

12) PC[M+CH₃COO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC	MS Level for identification	MS ¹ , MS ²
Identification level	Molecular species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M+CH ₃ COO]-
Isotope correction at MS ¹	Type 2	MS ² adduct	[M-H]-
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
FA1(+O)			
FA2(+O)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ¹ verified by standard	No
MS ² verified by standard	No	Background check at MS ¹	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes
Which assumptions were presumed?	Chemical formula constraints	Check on:	Isobaric overlap
Limit of detection	S/N ratio	Lipid Identification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes		

12) PC[M+CH₃COO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
PC 34:0;0 (17:0;0/17:0;0)		PC	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No

Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Batch correction	No		

13) PC O[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC O	MS Level for identification	MS ¹ , MS ²
Identification level	Molecular species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M+CH3COO]-
Isotope correction at MS ¹	Type 2	MS ² adduct	[M-H]-
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
FA2(+O)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ¹ verified by standard	No
MS ² verified by standard	No	Background check at MS ¹	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes
Which assumptions were presumed?	Chemical formula constraints	Check on:	Isobaric overlap
Limit of detection	S/N ratio	Lipid Identification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes		

13) PC O[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
PC 34:0;0 (17:0;0/17:0;0)		PC O	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Batch correction	No		

14) PC P[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC P	MS Level for identification	MS ¹ , MS ²
Identification level	Molecular species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M+CH3COO]-
Isotope correction at MS ¹	Type 2	MS ² adduct	[M-H]-
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
FA2(+O)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ¹ verified by standard	No
MS ² verified by standard	No	Background check at MS ¹	Yes

Background check at MS ²	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes
Which assumptions were presumed?	Chemical formula constraints	Check on:	Isobaric overlap
Limit of detection	S/N ratio	Lipid Identification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes		

14) PC P[M+CH₃COO]⁻ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
PC 34:0;0 (17:0;0/17:0;0)		PC P	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Batch correction	No		

15) PE[M-H]⁻ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE	MS Level for identification	MS ¹ , MS ²
Identification level	Molecular species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M-H] ⁻
Isotope correction at MS ¹	Type 2	MS ² adduct	[M-H] ⁻
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
FA1(+O)			
FA2(+O)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ¹ verified by standard	No
MS ² verified by standard	No	Background check at MS ¹	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes
Which assumptions were presumed?	Chemical formula constraints	Check on:	Isobaric overlap
Limit of detection	S/N ratio	Lipid Identification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes		

15) PE[M-H]⁻ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
PE 34:0;0 (17:0;0/17:0;0)		PE	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Batch correction	No		

16) PE O[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE O	MS Level for identification	MS ¹ , MS ²
Identification level	Molecular species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M-H]-
Isotope correction at MS ¹	Type 2	MS ² adduct	[M-H]-
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
FA2(+O)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ¹ verified by standard	No
MS ² verified by standard	No	Background check at MS ¹	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes
Which assumptions were presumed?	Chemical formula constraints	Check on:	Isobaric overlap
Limit of detection	S/N ratio	Lipid Identification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes		

16) PE O[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
PE 34:0;0 (17:0;0/17:0;0)		PE O	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Batch correction	No		

17) PE P[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE P	MS Level for identification	MS ¹ , MS ²
Identification level	Molecular species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M-H]-
Isotope correction at MS ¹	Type 2	MS ² adduct	[M-H]-
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
FA2(+O)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ¹ verified by standard	No
MS ² verified by standard	No	Background check at MS ¹	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes
Which assumptions were presumed?	Chemical formula constraints	Check on:	Isobaric overlap
Limit of detection	S/N ratio	Lipid Identification Software	Lipotype Xplorer

Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes		

17) PE P[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
PE 34:0;0 (17:0;0/17:0;0)		PE P	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Batch correction	No		

18) PI[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PI	MS Level for identification	MS ¹ , MS ²
Identification level	Molecular species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M-H]-
Isotope correction at MS ¹	Type 2	MS ² adduct	[M-H]-
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
FA1(+O)			
FA2(+O)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ¹ verified by standard	No
MS ² verified by standard	No	Background check at MS ¹	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes
Which assumptions were presumed?	Chemical formula constraints	Check on:	Isobaric overlap
Limit of detection	S/N ratio	Lipid Identification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes		

18) PI[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
PI 32:0;0 (16:0;0/16:0;0)		PI	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Batch correction	No		

19) SM[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	SM	MS Level for identification	MS ¹
Identification level	Species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M+CH3COO]-
Isotope correction at MS ¹	Type 2	MS ¹ verified by standard	No
Background check at MS ¹	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes
Which assumptions were presumed?	Chemical formula constraints	Limit of detection	S/N ratio
Lipid Identification Software	Lipotype Xplorer	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes		

19) SM[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
SM 30:1;O2 (18:1;O2/12:0;0)		SM	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Batch correction	No		

20) TG[M+NH4]+ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	TG	MS Level for identification	MS ¹ , MS ²
Identification level	Species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M+NH4]+
Isotope correction at MS ¹	Type 2	MS ² adduct	[M+NH4]+
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
-FA1(+HO)-(NH3)			
-FA2(+HO)-(NH3)			
-FA3(+HO)-(NH3)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ¹ verified by standard	No
MS ² verified by standard	No	Background check at MS ¹	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes
Which assumptions were presumed?	Chemical formula constraints	Check on:	Isobaric overlap
Limit of detection	S/N ratio	Lipid Identification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes		

20) TG[M+NH4]+ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			

Internal standard	Endogenous subclass
TG 51:0;0 (17:0;0/17:0;0/17:0;0)	TG

Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Batch correction	No		

21) CL[M-2H]2- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	CL	MS Level for identification	MS ¹ , MS ²
Identification level	Species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M-2H]2-
Isotope correction at MS ¹	Type 2	MS ² adduct	[M-H]-

Fragments for identification

Fragment name
FA1(+O)
FA2(+O)
FA3(+O)
FA4(+O)

Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ¹ verified by standard	No
MS ² verified by standard	No	Background check at MS ¹	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes
Which assumptions were presumed?	Chemical formula constraints	Check on:	Isobaric overlap
Limit of detection	S/N ratio	Lipid Identification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes		

21) CL[M-2H]2- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			

Internal standard	Endogenous subclass
CL 56:0;0 (14:0;0/14:0;0/14:0;0/14:0;0)	CL

Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Batch correction	No		

22) LPA[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPA	MS Level for identification	MS ¹
Identification level	Species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M-H]-
Isotope correction at MS ¹	Type 2	MS ¹ verified by standard	No

Background check at MS ¹	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes
Which assumptions were presumed?	Chemical formula constraints	Limit of detection	S/N ratio
Lipid Identification Software	Lipotype Xplorer	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes		

22) LPA[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
LPA 17:0;0		LPA	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Batch correction	No		

23) LPG[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPG	MS Level for identification	MS ¹
Identification level	Species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M-H]-
Isotope correction at MS ¹	Type 2	MS ¹ verified by standard	No
Background check at MS ¹	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes
Which assumptions were presumed?	Chemical formula constraints	Limit of detection	S/N ratio
Lipid Identification Software	Lipotype Xplorer	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes		

23) LPG[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
LPG 17:1;0		LPG	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Batch correction	No		

24) LPI[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPI	MS Level for identification	MS ¹
Identification level	Species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M-H]-
Isotope correction at MS ¹	Type 2	MS ¹ verified by standard	No
Background check at MS ¹	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes
Which assumptions were presumed?	Chemical formula constraints	Limit of detection	S/N ratio
Lipid Identification Software	Lipotype Xplorer	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes		

24) LPI[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
LPI 17:1;0		LPI	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Batch correction	No		

25) LPS[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPS	MS Level for identification	MS ¹
Identification level	Species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M-H]-
Isotope correction at MS ¹	Type 2	MS ¹ verified by standard	No
Background check at MS ¹	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes
Which assumptions were presumed?	Chemical formula constraints	Limit of detection	S/N ratio
Lipid Identification Software	Lipotype Xplorer	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes		

25) LPS[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
LPS 17:1;0		LPS	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Batch correction	No		

26) PA[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PA	MS Level for identification	MS ¹ , MS ²
Identification level	Molecular species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M-H]-
Isotope correction at MS ¹	Type 2	MS ² adduct	[M-H]-
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
FA1(+O)			
FA2(+O)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ¹ verified by standard	No
MS ² verified by standard	No	Background check at MS ¹	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes
Which assumptions were presumed?	Chemical formula constraints	Check on:	Isobaric overlap
Limit of detection	S/N ratio	Lipid Identification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes		

26) PA[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
PA 34:0;0 (17:0;0/17:0;0)		PA	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Batch correction	No		

27) PS[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PS	MS Level for identification	MS ¹ , MS ²
Identification level	Molecular species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M-H]-
Isotope correction at MS ¹	Type 2	MS ² adduct	[M-H]-
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
FA1(+O)			
FA2(+O)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ¹ verified by standard	No
MS ² verified by standard	No	Background check at MS ¹	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes
Which assumptions were presumed?	Chemical formula constraints	Check on:	Isobaric overlap
Limit of detection	S/N ratio	Lipid Identification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes

Nomenclature for fragment ions Yes

27) PS[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
PS 34:0;0 (17:0;0/17:0;0)		PS	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Lipotype Xplorer
Batch correction	No		
